

Endoscopic Extraction of Impacted Stones at Choledochoduodenostomy Site Using Tripod Grasper Forceps: A Rare Case Report

Min Nay Zar Wyke¹, Zaw Min Naing², Ye Zaw Htwe², Kyaw Ye Naung Htun³, Kyaw Thu Linn³, Thant Lwyn San⁴, Khin Aung Htun⁵

¹Senior Consultant Surgeon, No. (1) Military Hospital (700-Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar.

¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0986-1047>

²Endoscopy Nurse, No. (1) Military Hospital (700-Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar.

³Consultant Surgeon, No. (1) Military Hospital (700-Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar.

⁴Professor and Head of Department of Surgery, Defence Services Medical Academy, Yangon, Myanmar.

⁵Rector and Senior Consultant Surgeon, Defence Services Medical Academy, Yangon, Myanmar.

ABSTRACT

A 37-year-old man presented with acute epigastric pain radiating to the back after a heavy meal during military duty, associated with bilious vomiting, fever with chills and rigors, constipation, profuse sweating, and respiratory discomfort. He had undergone cholecystectomy, choledochotomy, choledocholithotomy, and choledochoduodenostomy two months earlier for gallstones, common bile duct (CBD) stones, and intrahepatic duct (IHD) stones. Intraoperatively, some intrahepatic stones could not be extracted due to technical limitations. On current admission, initial conservative management was given for suspected acute gastritis. Ultrasound abdomen revealed pneumobilia without pancreatitis. Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (OGD) surprisingly revealed stone impaction at the choledochoduodenostomy site in the first part of the duodenum (D1). Endoscopic extraction with basket and balloon failed, but successful stone crushing with rat-tooth forceps followed by removal with tripod foreign body forceps retrieved two large stones. The patient improved significantly, with subsequent imaging confirming residual small intrahepatic stones. He was discharged two weeks after admission in stable condition. This case highlights the rare complication of stone impaction at a choledochoduodenostomy site and the therapeutic efficacy of endoscopic intervention.

KEYWORDS: Choledochoduodenostomy, biliary stone impaction, endoscopic stone extraction, common bile duct stones, intrahepatic duct stones, epigastric pain, pneumobilia, tripod grasper forceps.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
18 September 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Choledochoduodenostomy (CDD) is a surgical procedure frequently performed in complex biliary diseases where multiple common bile duct (CBD) or intrahepatic duct (IHD) stones are present. It provides a permanent biliary-enteric drainage pathway that facilitates bile flow and clearance of small stones (1). Despite its utility, CDD is not free from complications, particularly when intrahepatic stones remain unremoved during surgery (2).

Recurrent stone formation, sump syndrome, cholangitis, and anastomotic strictures are well-documented sequelae after

CDD. However, early postoperative stone impaction at the anastomotic site is rare. Such impaction may cause acute abdominal pain, mimic gastritis or pancreatitis, and be difficult to diagnose by routine imaging (3).

In recent years, endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) and related techniques have revolutionized the diagnosis and treatment of biliary diseases (4). In patients with altered anatomy such as CDD, direct endoscopic visualization during esophagogastroduodenoscopy (OGD) can provide important diagnostic clues and therapeutic opportunities (5).

Endoscopic Extraction of Impacted Stones at Choledochoduodenostomy Site Using Tripod Grasper Forceps: A Rare Case Report

The military population often returns to strenuous duty earlier than recommended, predisposing them to early recurrence or exacerbation of surgical sequelae. This unique occupational factor must be considered in clinical evaluation and postoperative follow-up. We present the case of a young man who developed symptomatic biliary stone impaction at the choledochoduodenostomy site two months after surgery, successfully managed by endoscopic stone crushing and extraction.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 37-year-old man presented to our hospital with acute epigastric pain for two days following a heavy meal while on duty. The pain radiated to the back and was associated with three episodes of vomiting of bile-stained fluid and undigested food, fever with chills and rigor, constipation, profuse sweating, and transient respiratory discomfort.

Two months earlier, he had been operated at our hospital for obstructive jaundice. Imaging studies including ultrasound and contrast-enhanced CT revealed a distended gallbladder with a 0.5 cm gallstone, choledocholithiasis with the largest CBD stone measuring 1.3 cm, and multiple stones in the common hepatic duct (CHD) and both intrahepatic ducts with biliary dilatation. He underwent open cholecystectomy, choledochotomy, choledocholithotomy, and choledochoduodenostomy. However, extraction of intrahepatic stones was not feasible due to lack of advanced facilities. His recovery was uneventful, and he was followed up twice postoperatively. Despite medical advice, he resumed active duty early without adequate rest.

On admission, his general condition was fair. He was afebrile, with blood pressure 110/70 mmHg and pulse rate 80/min. There was no pallor or jaundice. Abdominal examination revealed mild epigastric tenderness. Based on clinical findings, acute severe gastritis was suspected initially.

He was managed conservatively with nil-by-mouth (NBM), nasogastric tube insertion with hourly suction, intravenous fluids, antibiotics, pantoprazole, analgesics, and antispasmodics. Laboratory investigations showed hemoglobin 13.9 g/dL, WBC count $11.1 \times 10^9/L$, platelet count $312 \times 10^9/L$, elevated liver enzymes (two-fold), and serum amylase of 80 U/L. Plain abdominal X-ray was negative for gastric outlet obstruction or intestinal obstruction.

Figure 1. Endoscopic views of the oesophagus, stomach, and duodenum demonstrating normal mucosa.

Ultrasound of the abdomen revealed air within the biliary tree (pneumbilia), consistent with the patient's previous choledochoduodenostomy (CDD), with no evidence of acute pancreatitis. Despite conservative management, the patient's symptoms persisted, prompting further evaluation. On the third day of admission, esophagogastroduodenoscopy (OGD) was performed to assess the upper gastrointestinal tract for potential gastric or duodenal pathology. Endoscopic examination revealed healthy mucosa of the esophagus, stomach, and duodenum, with no signs of ulceration, erosion, or mucosal inflammation (Figure 1).

Figure 2. Endoscopic views showing impacted biliary stones obstructing the choledochoduodenostomy anastomosis site in the first part of the duodenum (D1).

Unexpectedly, a serendipitous finding of impacted stones was observed at the choledochoduodenostomy (CDD) anastomosis site in the first part of the duodenum (D1). The stones appeared as firm, yellowish-brown masses completely obstructing the anastomotic opening, with no associated mucosal ulceration or bleeding (Figure 2). The appearance was highly suggestive of residual biliary stones that had migrated from the intrahepatic ducts and become

Endoscopic Extraction of Impacted Stones at Choledochoduodenostomy Site Using Tripod Grasper Forceps: A Rare Case Report

lodged at the anastomosis, explaining the patient's persistent symptoms.

Figure 3. Endoscopic views demonstrating attempted stone extraction using a retrieval basket device at the choledochoduodenostomy anastomosis site.

Initial attempts at stone extraction using a standard retrieval basket were unsuccessful, as the stones were tightly impacted (Figure 3). A subsequent attempt with a balloon catheter also failed to dislodge the stones due to their large size, hardness, and firm impaction against the mucosal margins (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Endoscopic views showing attempts at stone extraction with a balloon catheter device at the choledochoduodenostomy anastomosis site.

Given the failure of conventional extraction techniques, stone crushing was carefully initiated at the periphery of the stones using rat-tooth forceps (Figure 5). This deliberate edge-crushing technique allowed partial mobilization and size reduction of the stones while minimizing trauma to the surrounding mucosa.

Figure 5. Endoscopic views showing stone crushing at the margins of the impacted stone using rat-tooth forceps (edge-crushing technique).

Figure 6. Endoscopic views showing retrieval of the impacted CDD stone using a tripod grasper forceps.

Figure 7. Endoscopic views showing retrieval of the second impacted CDD stone with tripod grasper forceps. After achieving sufficient crushing, two large stones were grasped and successfully extracted using a Medwork® Tripod Forceps, which provided a secure three-pronged grip for removal (Figure 6, 7 & 9).

Following extraction, the CDD site was thoroughly irrigated with water to flush out small debris and confirm patency. Endoscopic inspection demonstrated a clear anastomotic lumen, with both proximal and distal ends of the anastomosis free of residual stone material (Figure 8). The procedure was well tolerated, with no evidence of mucosal

Endoscopic Extraction of Impacted Stones at Choledochoduodenostomy Site Using Tripod Grasper Forceps: A Rare Case Report

injury or bleeding, and resulted in immediate symptomatic relief.

Figure 8. Endoscopic views confirming complete stone clearance at the choledochoduodenostomy site after extraction of two impacted biliary stones using a tripod grasper forceps (red arrow – distal end; blue arrow – proximal end of the anastomosis).

The patient's symptoms improved immediately after the procedure. He resumed oral intake and was closely monitored. Follow-up CT abdomen demonstrated pneumobilia with mild dilatation of both intrahepatic ducts and revealed small intrahepatic ductal stones measuring 0.2 cm in segment V, 0.5 cm in segment VI, and 0.6 cm in segment VII of the right hepatic lobe, with an intact choledochoduodenostomy anastomosis. He was discharged two weeks later in stable condition, with advice for further follow-up and monitoring.

Figure 9. Two extracted biliary stones (measuring 1.6 cm and 1.4 cm) with the Medwork® Tripod Forceps used for retrieval.

DISCUSSION

Choledochoduodenostomy has long been an accepted surgical procedure for complex biliary stone disease. Its success depends on effective clearance of CBD and IHD

stones during surgery. Incomplete removal of intrahepatic stones can predispose to early recurrence or impaction at the anastomotic site.

In the present case, intrahepatic stones were left behind due to lack of advanced equipment, creating a risk for subsequent complications. The patient's premature return to active duty further increased the risk of early stone migration and impaction.

The clinical presentation mimicked acute severe gastritis and partially overlapped with features of pancreatitis. The presence of pneumobilia on ultrasound was an expected finding after CDD, but it masked the underlying stone impaction. Thus, routine imaging modalities were insufficient for diagnosis.

Endoscopy proved to be both diagnostic and therapeutic. Visualization of the impacted stone at the CDD site during OGD was serendipitous, as the procedure was initially intended to evaluate for gastritis. Endoscopic extraction with basket and balloon techniques often succeeds, but in this patient, these failed due to the size and firmness of the stones.

Mechanical crushing with rat-tooth forceps followed by removal with tripod grasper forceps was innovative and effective. Tripod grasper forceps, although primarily designed for foreign body retrieval, can serve as an effective tool for extracting large or impacted biliary stones when standard baskets and balloons fail. This highlights the need for flexibility and improvisation in endoscopic management when conventional tools fail.

This case is noteworthy for the innovative stepwise endoscopic approach used to manage impacted stones at a choledochoduodenostomy site. Conventional extraction techniques with basket and balloon devices are generally first-line methods; however, in this patient, these failed due to the size, hardness, and firm impaction of the stones. The use of a deliberate edge-crushing technique with rat-tooth forceps allowed safe fragmentation and partial mobilization of the stones, reducing their size and making subsequent removal feasible. Following fragmentation, the application of the Medwork Tripod Forceps provided a secure three-pronged grasp, enabling successful extraction of two large stones without complications. This combined approach demonstrates that, when standard methods fail, mechanical crushing at the stone margins followed by tripod forceps-assisted extraction can be an effective and minimally invasive strategy for achieving complete clearance. To our knowledge, few reports have described this technique in the early postoperative setting after choledochoduodenostomy, underscoring the importance of procedural adaptability and instrument selection in complex biliary interventions.

The patient's rapid recovery after stone removal demonstrated the effectiveness of minimally invasive approaches in resolving post-CDD complications. Nevertheless, the presence of residual intrahepatic stones

Endoscopic Extraction of Impacted Stones at Choledochoduodenostomy Site Using Tripod Grasper Forceps: A Rare Case Report

remains a challenge. Post-extraction, careful follow-up with imaging such as CT or magnetic resonance cholangio-pancreatography (MRCP) is essential to exclude residual intrahepatic stones. Such patients require long-term follow-up, imaging surveillance, and possibly repeat interventions (9 &10).

In this case, the use of tripod grasper forceps proved advantageous in securing and extracting the impacted stones, highlighting its utility as an alternative endoscopic instrument in complex scenarios. This case also emphasizes the importance of postoperative rest and compliance in physically active individuals undergoing biliary surgery, as premature exertion may predispose to early complications.

CONCLUSION

Stone impaction at a choledochoduodenostomy site is a rare but clinically significant complication, especially in patients with residual intrahepatic stones. Endoscopy offers both diagnostic and therapeutic solutions, even when conventional retrieval devices fail. This case highlights the value of innovative endoscopic techniques with tripod grasper forceps and the importance of postoperative compliance, particularly in the military population.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to extend my heartfelt thanks to the endoscopic team of our hospital for their expertise and dedication in endoscopic management. I am especially grateful to the patient and his family for their kind cooperation and trust.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declared no potential conflict of interests with respect to authorship and publication of this article.

FUNDING

The authors received no specific funding for this case report and publication of this article.

REFERENCES

- I. Gibson, R.N., Yeong, M.L., and Madden, M.V. 1987. Choledochoduodenostomy: long-term results and complications. *Br J Surg*, 1987, 74(9): 822-825.
- II. Misra, S.P., Gulati, P., and Thorat, V.K. 1989. Complications following choledochoduodenostomy. *Am J Gastroenterol*, 1989, 84(6): 624-627.
- III. Liau, K.H., Venkatesh, S.K., Ho, and C.K. 2006. Biliary-enteric anastomosis: Complications and management. *Ann Acad Med Singapore*, 2006, 35(2): 94-101.
- IV. Williams, E.J., Green, J., Beckingham, I., Parks, R., Martin, D., and Lombard, M. 2008. Guidelines on the management of common bile duct stones (CBDS). *Gut*, 2008, 57(7): 1004-1021.
- V. Costamagna, G., Tringali, A., and Mutignani, M. 2012. Endoscopic management of common bile duct stones: A review. *Clin Endosc*, 2012, 45(3): 220-226.
- VI. Hong, W.D., Zhu, Q.H., and Huang, Q.K. 2014. Endoscopic sphincterotomy plus endoscopic papillary large balloon dilation vs endoscopic sphincterotomy for choledocholithiasis. *World J Gastroenterol*, 2014, 20(39): 13946-13951.
- VII. Testoni, P.A., Mariani, A., Aabakken, L., et al. 2016. Papillary cannulation and sphincterotomy techniques at ERCP: ESGE Clinical Guideline. *Endoscopy*, 2016, 48(7): 657-683.
- VIII. Cotton, P.B., and Leung, J.W. *Advanced Digestive Endoscopy: ERCP*. Wiley-Blackwell, 2005.
- IX. Chen, Y.K., and Pleskow, D.K. 1996. Management of difficult bile duct stones. *Gastrointest Endosc Clin N Am*, 1996, 6(1): 123-140.
- X. Uchiyama, K., et al. 2003. Long-term prognosis after choledochoduodenostomy. *Surgery*, 2003, 133(6): 639-643.